

Towards workplace flexibility: Flexitime arrangements in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Purpose- to present and discuss the findings of a study on flexitime as a novel people management practice emerging in Sri Lanka. Specifically, to present and discuss: factors that predict the level of satisfaction with flexitime, differences in attitudes towards flexitime, the effectiveness of flexitime as a strategy to attract and retain employees, and barriers that hinder its use.

Design/methodology/approach- 108 employees involved in producing IT related output as his/her primary job function, from 30 software development companies, responded to the self-administered survey questionnaire. In analysis, univariate, bivariate and multivariate techniques were adopted.

Findings- flexitime allowed autonomy to employees to harmonize work and non work demands upon their time result in better workplace relations. Overall, findings support for the non-traditional approach to people management. However, findings have important implications for the design or modification of flexitime arrangements.

Originality/value- majority of flexitime research is criticized for its theoretical nature, failure to include statistical treatment of data and failure to pay specific attention to managerial and professional employees. Further, there is a marked absence of research-led literature in developing countries to clarify the way in which non-traditional people management practices work in different contexts. Specifically, no such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka.

Keyword(s): Flexitime, Human resource management, IT industry, People management, Sri Lanka, Workplace flexibility.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

The resources involved in economic activity have been categorised into people, capital and technology (MacLean, 2006). In the competitive environment, organizations have realised that people or human resource is the critical component to success as they drive capital growth and technological expansion. People are all different and they have different profiles: they bring different life and employment experiences, qualifications, interests, skills, abilities and competencies. However, people need care and attention to effectively and consistently perform at a high level (Updegraff, 2004). New people management ideas, technologies and practices have been replacing the old ones (Noon and Blyton 1997). An example is workplace flexibility (Johnson, 2004). Changes in the nature of employment towards flexibility have been seen as an attempt to address changing organisational and environmental requirements (Twina et al, 2006); the use of workplace flexibility strategies has been increasing. Organizational flexibility strategies could be identified as internal flexibility, external flexibility, quantitative or numerical flexibility and qualitative or functional flexibility (Johnson, 2004). Internal flexibility is related to the ability to cope with fluctuations and changes in the demand for labour by using the existing workforce (for instance, overtime, flexible working hours). In contrast, external flexibility refers to making use of external labour when necessary (for instance by using temporary contracts). Quantitative or numerical flexibility is related to the variation of the amount of work (for instance, number of workers, number of working hours). Qualitative or functional flexibility is related to the ability to vary the content of work in connection with the qualification of workers (job rotation, horizontal and vertical mobility) (see- Looise et al, 1998). Each of these strategies brings different advantages and disadvantages for both organizations and employees (Johnson, 2004). Yet,

organizations need to have a vision of future organisation and future worker in order to manage necessary structural, technological and psychological changes involved in using any of these strategies (Strachan and Burgess, 1998; Huws et al., 1996). Thus, for the employer and for the employee workplace flexibility mean previously uncharted challenges, as both parties attempt to create a working relationship, which simultaneously recognises and realizes the needs of the organizations and the worker. Hence, interest in researching workplace flexibility strategies has been growing (Dex and Scheibl, 2001). Empirical studies have shown that flexitime also known as flexible work hours, which is a form of internal flexibility, was the most frequently utilized and the most preferred arrangement over any other workplace flexibility strategies (Galpin and Skinner 2004; Lo, 2003; Solomon, 1994). Though enhanced employees' sense of control over working time has been identified as the most cherished management prerogatives (Elbing et al 1975; Narayanan and Nath, 1982), the majority of empirical research was conducted on other forms of workplace flexibility (see- Creagh and Brewster, 1998; Croucher and Brewster, 1998; Drew and Murtagh, 2005; Dyer, 1998; Gunnigle et al, 1998; Looise et al, 1998; Mayne et al, 1996; McCartney and Evans, 2005; Nadeem and Hendry, 2003; Papalexandris and Kramar, 1997; Raghuram et al, 2001; Sheridan and Conway, 2001; Smith and Wedderburn, 1998; Tomlinson, 2004; Tüselmann, 1996; Voudouris, 2004). Therefore, in this paper the focus is specifically on flexitime arrangements and to report empirical evidence from Sri Lanka. In order to provide the context for the paper, the next three sections provide brief descriptions on flexitime, why a study on flexitime is important in Asian developing countries, Sri Lanka in particular, and a brief description on the Sri Lankan context, respectively. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings.

Flexitime

Flexitime refers to a policy in which the traditional fixed times that full time employees start and finish the working day are replaced by a framework within which employees are allowed some freedom to choose their starting and quitting times (Golembiewski, et al, 1975; Hicks and Klimoski, 1981; Olorunsola and Ibegbulam, 2003). Flexitime is in operation as a part of HR benefit package offered to employees (Scandura and Lankau, 1997). Although there are a number of variations in its form, the basic model of flexitime usually consists of five interrelated components: (1) a bandwidth within which all hours must be worked- say, 6:00am to 6:30pm, (2) a core time during which all employees are required to be working, as, for example, from ten to twelve in the morning and two to four in the afternoon, (3) a flexible band of hours before, after, or in between core times that allows employees to exercise designated options regarding their presence in, or absence from, the work place, (4) banking, which allows carry-over of surplus or deficient hours worked, and (5) variability of schedule - the employees' freedom to vary working hours from one period to another without prior approval from their supervisor (Golembiewski & Proehl, 1978). The degree of flexibility and the amount of discretion permitted to employees depend on the variations in the above five components in the program (Kim and Campagna, 1981). Either operational, managerial or professional work settings can accommodate flexitime (Almer and Kaplan, 2002). It is the technical requirements of the work and the way in which workflows are organized that determine whether the system will work (Owen, 1977). As a HR practice, flexitime provides considerable benefits to both employer and employee (see- Cohen and Single, 2001; Evans, 1973; Latona, 1981; Ronen, 1981; Rubin, 1979). However, individual differences influence

the extent to which flexitime gives benefits to employees and its impact on job related attitudes and career outcomes; hence their responses to flexitime (Almer and Kaplan, 2002; Albion, 2004). However, few studies revealed that organizations had not installed flexitime as there were practical issues related to it (see- Field, 1996; Forrier and Sels 2003; Kush and Stroh, 1994; Scheibl and Dex 1998).

Why conduct a study on flexitime in Sri Lanka

For four main reasons, research into flexitime arrangements of an Asian developing country, Sri Lanka in particular, is important. First, though considerable amount of literature addressed flexitime, majority is criticized for its theoretical nature, anecdotal reports, and the failure to include statistical treatment of data (Pierce and Newstrom, 1983; Rau and Hyland, 2002; Scandura and Lankau, 1997). Further there is a need to revalidate the findings of the empirical studies conducted on flexitime several decades ago as evidence suggest that many changes have been taking place related to work itself and the practice of work (Kramar, 1998; Shamir, 1980). Furthermore, very little work has been directed towards the identification of design features for flexitime (Narayanan and Nath, 1982; Pierce and Newstrom, 1983; Scandura and Lankau, 1997). Second, only few research into workplace flexibility paid specific attention to managerial and professional employees. However findings of those studies are not conclusive (see-Almer and Kaplan, 2002; Cohen and Single, 2001; Narayanan and Nath, 1982; Mattis, 1990). Thus, more studies warrant in this area. Third, most of the research-led literature on HRM/IR area are based in the Western context or in newly industrialized countries and there is a marked absence of research-led literature in this regard for developing countries (see-Guest, 1997; Khatri, 2000; Shadur and Tung, 1997; Chandrakumara and Sparrow, 2004;

Budhwar, 2003). Asian domestic organizations' move towards operating in global market and developing global strategies impact on their work and employment practices and influence them to move towards a strategic approach to people management (see- Brewster et al. 1996; Budhwar, 2000; Budhwar and Debrah, 2001a, 2001b; Budhwar and Sparrow, 1998; Debrah and Smith, 2000a, 2000b; Dowling et al., 1994; Venkata Ratnam, 1995; Yadapadithaya, 2000). Further, liberalization of economies in Asia created considerable employment opportunities for those, including women, who possess marketable skills and talent (Budhwar et al, 2005). In this context, workplace flexibility is identified as a step towards implementing policies that help to create a women-friendly work environment to attract and retain women (see- Nath, 2000; Remery et al, 2003). However, there is no enough clarity as to how such initiatives work in practice (see- Budhwar et al, 2005; Budhwar and Boyne, 2004; Budhwar and Khatri, 2001; Hofstede, 1993; Poole, 1990; Sparrow and Budhwar, 1997). Finally, Sri Lanka offers a liberal and dynamic investment environment (see- Chandrakumara and Budhwar, 2005). Though economic globalisation with outsourcing business environment impacts on work and employment, research-led literature in the Sri Lankan context is rare. In a study Akuratiyagamage and Opatha (2004) found that hours of work caused a high level of grievance to managers and there were slight variations in the level of grievance suffered by gender. However, specifically no studies have been conducted on workplace flexibility strategies in the Sri Lankan context. The preliminary investigations into Sri Lankan firms revealed that IT sector have begun to experiment with flexitime for managerial and professional employees. Thus, specific aims of this paper are to present and discuss empirical results from the survey in software development companies on: employee level of work satisfaction with flexitime and factors that predict level of satisfaction; employee attitudes towards flexitime and differences in attitudes in terms of age, gender, marital status, the level

of education, and the number of employees in the organization; the extent to which organisations could use flexitime as a strategy to attract and retain employees; reasons that hinder its use. Though there are two forms of flexitime- formal and informal (Hall and Atkinson, 2006; Golden, 2001), in the study organization led formal flexitime arrangements are investigated.

The Sri Lankan context

Development initiatives through foreign direct investments and domestic investments led to create new business sectors in Sri Lanka. One of such fastest growing business sectors contributing to economic growth since 1990s is information technology (IT). The developments in IT sector led to a growth of a professional and technical middle class in Sri Lanka (Flecker and Huws, 2003). As IT firms build on knowledge workers, absorbing suitable personnel is the focal point. In terms of 'education for all' philosophy, Sri Lanka is the only country that provides free education for all citizens of the country from primary education to the graduation. In addition, other higher educational institutions and private training centres provide a wide range of IT training courses, which also help to increase IT labour market. However, IT firms adopt various 'poaching' strategies to recruit IT personnel creating a high labour turnover in the sector (Jinadasa and Wickramasinghe, 2005). This not only influences performance and stability of the sector but also increases the costs of recruitment and selection (Jinadasa and Wickramasinghe, 2005).

According to Department of Census and Statistics (2005), the total working age population of the country was 16.9 million in 2005, of which 48% were economically active- 67% males

and 33% females. However, there is no significant change in labour force participation rate in year 2005, compared to previous years. Sri Lanka is trying to promote gender equality in terms of increasing women's participation in the workforce and in terms of the range of jobs open to them. When considering the specific segregation of data on IT labour market, at the end of 2004, total employment in the IT sector was just slightly over 20,000, which is a growth of 30 per cent from 2003. Only 22 per cent of the IT workforce is female but this is an increase as in 1998 it was only 17 per cent (SLICTA, 2005). Though no specific segregation of data based on education levels of IT labour force is available by gender, of the employed females, 22 per cent have an educational qualification of General Certificate in Education (Advanced Level) or above, compared to a proportion of 13 percent employed males having the same level of education. Thus, an increasing number of educated women enter into the economically active population and this trend is projected to continue (Department of Census and Statistics, 2005).

In the above context, a number of adjustments and adaptations in people management practices have to be introduced to address the needs of diversified workforce. Thus, the study aimed at investigating flexitime arrangements as a novel people management practice emerging in the IT sector in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

Sample

For the study "a person involved in producing IT related output as his/her primary job function" is how an employee is described and the study was confined to software development companies. The sample selection was conducted in two stages. First, a random

sample of 40 software development companies that are registered under Companies Act of Sri Lanka (No. 17 of 1982) were selected as such organizations follow the rules, procedures, accounting and reporting requirements for companies incorporated in Sri Lanka. Second, from those randomly selected companies, a random sample of employees was selected. Of the 145 questionnaires distributed among the 40 companies, 112 employees belong to 30 companies voluntarily responded within 3 weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 108 usable responses resulted in a 74 per cent response rate. This is a very acceptable rate in the context of a developing country (see-Nyambegera et al, 2000) and also the response rate is considered as adequate (Baruch, 1999; Roth and BeVier, 1998).

Table I shows the characteristics of 30 companies included in the sample. 15 companies reported the use of flexitime though there are slight variations in the arrangements adopted. All had a bandwidth and core work hours, and flexitime was implemented to all jobs if judged feasible.

Take in Table I

Table II shows the characteristics of 108 respondents included in the sample. The age categorization revealed that all 108 respondents belonged to the age group of 25 to 35 years of age. This may be due to the nature of Sri Lankan software development industry, which is young. The z statistic and associated significance value of Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test indicated that the shape of the two distributions of employees from the companies in which flexitime exists and does not exist is not significantly different for gender (K-S $z=.068$, $p>.05$), marital status (K-S $z=.075$, $p>.05$), years of experience (K-S $z=.46$, $p>.05$), and

highest level of education (K-S $z=.638$, $p>.05$). Further, K-S test indicated that the shape of the two distributions of males and females in the total sample ($n=108$) is not significantly different for marital status (K-S $z=.246$, $p>.05$), highest level of education (K-S $z=.396$, $p>.05$), years of experience (K-S $z=.560$, $p>.05$), and number of employees in the workplace (K-S $z=.799$, $p>.05$). Furthermore, K-S test indicated that the shape of the two distributions of males and females in the companies with flexitime ($n=55$) is not significantly different for marital status (K-S $z=.356$, $p>.05$), highest level of education (K-S $z=.304$, $p>.05$), years of experience (K-S $z=.727$, $p>.05$), and number of employees in the workplace (K-S $z=.412$, $p>.05$).

Take in Table II

Data collection instrument and data analysis

The self-administered questionnaire was chosen as the main mode for data collection and it was designed to address all the objectives of the investigation. Following Scandura and Lankau (1997), the term “individual’s level of work satisfaction with flexitime” was defined as the “overall summary evaluation an individual makes regarding his/her work environment with flexitime”. The responses were recorded on Likert type five point scale (1=strongly disagree, 5= strongly agree). The questionnaire was piloted prior final distribution. In analysing items of level of work satisfaction and attitudes towards flexitime, responses from employees with flexitime were used. In analysing whether companies could use flexitime in attracting and retaining employees, all responses were used ($n=108$). As some companies were identified as not offering flexitime, it was decided to investigate reasons behind. Thus, as

the second stage, using a short questionnaire, information from employers where flexitime was not offered was obtained (n=15). By doing so, the research aimed to minimise the disadvantages of collecting survey data from one source (see- Khatri and Budhwar, 2002).

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS. Inter-item correlation test was conducted separately for positive statements and negative statements. Test results for both categories received standardized item alpha values higher than .7 (for positive statements: alpha .76 and negative statements: alpha .83). In the data analysis, in addition to descriptive statistics, correlation and multiple regression was used. In the analysis all nominal and ordinal data were recoded into two levels (for example- male=0, female=1). Regression analysis was run using stepwise method of model selection. In interpreting results, R-square (adjusted) statistics and standardized coefficients were used. The collinearity diagnostic confirmed that there are no problems with multicollinearity as variance inflation factor was less than two for the regression model resulted in. To investigate whether there are significant differences in attitudes towards flexitime in terms of gender and marital status, independent sample t-test was carried out while in terms of the level of education and the number of employees in the current workplace one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) between subjects analysis and post hoc tests were carried out.

Results

Level of work satisfaction with flexitime

The result for the level of work satisfaction with flexitime revealed that the employees indicated a high level of satisfaction ($\bar{X} = 4.33$, $SD = .54$). The results of the correlation

analyses are shown in table III. According to Table III, the number of employees in the current workplace is the most important in giving work satisfaction with flexitime.

Take in Table III

According to the results of the multiple regression, the number of employees in the current workplace had significant regression coefficient and it was positively associated with work satisfaction ($F = 4.160$, $\beta .272$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 55$). In other words, the number of employees in the current workplace along explained 6 percent ($R^2_{\text{adjusted}} = 0.056$) of the variance in work satisfaction.

Positive and negative attitudes towards flexitime

The results for attitudes towards flexitime are shown in table IV. 15 items (8 positive and 7 negative) were used to evaluate attitudes. Items marked with (N) indicate negative attitudes. As mentioned earlier, all items were rated on a 5 point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree, 5=strongly agree). High scores in positive attitude items and low scores in negative attitude items indicate favourable attitudes towards flexitime. As shown in table IV, all mean values indicate an overall positive evaluation of flexitime. Specifically, balancing work and family life ($\bar{X} = 4.40$), balancing work and social life ($\bar{X} = 4.24$) and reduction of stress ($\bar{X} = 4.16$) rated highly. It is also revealed that organizational members did not react negatively towards those who use flexitime ($\bar{X} = 1.71$), and had not felt as if important workplace events were

missed ($\bar{X} = 1.83$). However, there is a concern for the reduction in workplace learning opportunities. Past research also led to find that Sri Lankan organizations were reluctant to provide formal training and development opportunities for managerial and professional employees and such employees regarded daily organizational experiences as one of the best ways of learning (Akuratiyagamage, 2006 and 2005; Wickramasinghe, 2006).

Take in Table IV

The results for the differences in attitudes towards flexitime are shown in table V and VI. Table V shows results by gender. Levene's test for the equality of variance statistic for all items except 'leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues' had p-value for F less than .05. Therefore, for this item equal variance not assumed is used. For the items 'provide time for higher studies' ($t=2.103$; $p<0.05$), 'feel disconnected from the workplace' ($t= -1.841$; $p<0.05$), and 'leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues' ($t= -2.732$; $p<0.01$), t value is significant. A closer evaluation of these three items reveals different patterns of relationship for males and females. Females are more positive towards flexitime as it provides time for higher studies. However, males feel disconnected from workplace and believe that flexitime leads to difficulties in interacting with co-workers and superiors. Similar findings were also revealed by Albion (2004), Almer and Single (2004) and Narayanan and Nath (1982). Though Albion (2004) found flexitime cause to miss important work events, it is not supported in this research. Recent research (Lo, 2003; Albion, 2004) highlight that females indicate more favourable attitudes for flexitime in balancing work

and life. However in this research both males and females held a perception that flexitime helps in achieving work/life balance. Though career planning is one of the important areas of an individual's life (Budhwar and Baruch, 2003; Schuler et al, 2002), this investigation does not reveal that flexitime influence career aspirations of males and females differently ($t = -.721$; $p > 0.05$).

Table V also shows results by marital status. Levene's test for equality of variance statistic for all items except 'makes committed to work' had p-value for F less than .05. Therefore, for this item, equal variance not assumed is used. For the item 'provide time for higher studies' ($t = 2.361$; $p < 0.01$), t value is significant where unmarried people reveal more favourable attitudes towards flexitime.

Take in Table VI

Table VI shows results by the level of education and the number of employees in the current workplace. There were no significant differences in attitudes by the level of education. However, by the number of employees in the current workplace, there are significant differences in 7 items. Interestingly, for all these items respondents from the workplaces with less than 30 employees have concerns. This again supports the finding that the size of the workforce is an important factor in determining attitudes towards flexitime in the Sri Lankan context.

Take in Table VI

Flexitime as a strategy to attract and retain employees

The results for the extent to which organisations could use flexitime as a strategy to attract and retain employees are shown in table VII.

Take in Table VII

The results suggest that flexitime could be used as a strategy in attracting prospective employees but this would not be effective in retaining employees. Though Welch and Gordon (1980) found that flexitime lead an employee to stay with the employer for longer, this study does not support it. As the review of literature suggests (Debrah et al 2000; Jinadasa and Wickramasinghe, 2005), skills are transferable between employers and high rate of labour turnover prevail in the IT sector suggests that there could be a tendency for ‘poaching’ to occur.

Hindrance in the use of flexitime

The results for reasons that hinder the use of flexitime are shown in Table VIII (n=15). According to Table VIII, all companies unanimously strongly held a view that flexitime could make difficulties in coordinating interactions. The other items such as reduce team

spirit and reduce mutual learning opportunities obtained higher scores. The majority also identified company policies as barriers ($\bar{X} = 4.20$).

Take in Table VIII

Discussion and concluding remarks

The research investigated flexitime arrangements in Sri Lanka. The review of literature revealed that majority of the flexitime studies were conducted several decades back in the Western context. Further, many of those flexitime studies paid attention to lower-level employees. Hence, this study made an attempt to revalidate the findings of those studies in the Sri Lankan context. The study investigated perceptions of professional employees, who were from the software development companies, on flexitime arrangements in creating an appropriate professional environment for them.

First, the results of the investigation revealed that flexitime allowed autonomy to employees to harmonize work and non work demands upon their time. In other words, employees managed to develop work patterns which facilitate them to combine work and personal life commitments while employers reaping benefits of gaining employee commitment, loyalty and maximising employee potential. Though management of the work-family interface has become a managerial concern in the Western industrialized economies leading to the adoption of family-friendly or family-responsive policies, such institutional environment is not available in Sri Lanka. IT sector is the only sector known to be practicing flexitime in Sri Lanka. Thus, it is a new practice of work to Sri Lankans. The global outsourcing of IT jobs is

one of the fastest growing business areas in Sri Lanka as the country is identified as one of the promising investment destinations in the Asia Pacific region for outsourcing of IT jobs since the early 1990s (see- Flecker and Huws, 2003). When foreign investors increasingly outsource some elements of their production to Asian countries, like Sri Lanka, it could be assumed that they retained and transferred their preferred employment practices that they are accustomed to, such as flexitime, by challenging and changing the nature of prevalent employment practices in the Sri Lankan private sector to some extent.

Second, the findings of the study revealed that regardless of gender the majority felt that flexitime helped to balance work/life commitments. Based on the literature reviewed on flexitime arrangements in the other countries and on social cultural aspects of Asian countries, it could be assumed that females would prefer flexitime than males. However, the findings of the study had not revealed such. Between females and males, for the majority of aspects considered, there were no significant differences. Though there were no significant differences, females were more positive about their experiences with flexitime such as helps to balance work and social life. This might be due to the freedom that they gain to move out of their traditional household roles and develop a career in organizations. Recent statistics provide evidence to increasing number of young educated women entering economically active population. Further, evidence reveals that information technology services are increasing exponentially in contributing economic growth, and retract the promise of attractive employment that lead to a growth of a professional and technical middle class in Sri Lanka. While families may need two incomes, they may also require more flexible work arrangements in order to manage family demands when both parents are working. However, preference for flexitime does not only help for those with family responsibilities, flexitime

also accommodates the needs of those with other commitments, including sport, community involvement, other businesses and even recreational pursuits. Thus, flexitime is beneficial to workers at all stages of their careers by enabling a more holistic work/life balance. Thus, it could be concluded that flexitime becomes more important for both males and females. This strengthens the argument that both males and females prefer flexitime and this is not a gendered issue for the Sri Lankan sample. In this regard, the changes occurred in the Sri Lankan society as a result of the free education policy for all citizens of the country from primary education to the graduation, since 1945, are important. As a result of this education policy of the country, the majority of new entrants to the Sri Lankan labour force endowed with primary and secondary education. Further, since mid 1960s women entered the government administrative service (known as Ceylon Administrative Service). Such government policies helped to create an environment that has provided women equality at societal and political levels. Thus, it could be argued that the structure of the workforce has changed ever since, where male partner is the primary provider, by changing the work and employment in contemporary society.

Third, it was evident that the companies with larger number of employees offered flexitime more than companies with smaller number of employees. Thus, it could be argued that the greater the percentage of IT professionals in a software company's workforce, the more likely the organization will be to provide flexitime. This argument is based on the assumption that as the IT professionals in the workforce has grown, companies have become increasingly dependent on them and thus, more likely to be responsive on their needs. On the other hand, though flexitime arrangements in companies with smaller number of employees offered

limited benefits, employees use the option as it addresses some of their important preferences and needs.

Forth, the findings of the study led to reveal that employees accept flexitime as an important feature that they like to have in their future workplaces. Though previous studies show that employees on flexitime report lower turnover intentions than those on a standard work arrangement (see- Almer and Kaplan, 2002), the results of this study is contrary to such findings. In the Sri Lankan context, though flexitime as a strategy to be used to retain employees is questionable, when employees become conditioned to flexitime, they would be less likely to leave for another workplace where such an arrangement is not offered.

Finally, the employers from the organizations without flexitime are not yet convinced of the value it brings. They have concerns that flexitime would lead to anarchy in production, and that its costs would exceed any benefits to management. However, evidence from the workplaces in which flexitime implemented explains that it has been made to harmonize better workplace relations. Thus, employers have to consider positive outcomes in terms of the psychological contract between employer and employee that will ultimately affect work related attitudes of employees. On the other hand, when Asian domestic organizations locate themselves in a globally competitive outsourcing environment, there is a need of developing global employment strategies- like flexitime. In this regard, several research studies shown that Asian management systems are currently undergoing a rapid process of modernisation, where companies drive to modernise its management by grafting foreign work practices. In this connection, while business systems are competing in world markets, they have to adapt to dominant patterns in those markets. When concepts like flexitime enter into the play in the

forms of the requirements of foreign buyers or international best practices, those have a high degree of legitimacy. Thus, it could be assumed that this situation is explicit in the Sri Lankan context.

Implications

The results from the investigation have important implications for the design or modification of flexitime arrangements. First, the finding that the flexitime allowed autonomy to employees to harmonize work and non work demands imply that employees may work more effectively while on the job as they are at work at times when they are psychologically prepared. This could increase employees' overall positive feeling toward the employer resulting in better workplace relations. Overall, findings imply support for non-traditional approaches to people management as mentioned by Glueck (1979), Budhwar et al (2005), Lo (2003) and Albion (2004).

Second, the findings of the study led to imply that both males and females prefer flexitime. However, though males do like flexitime and they do not identify symptoms of organizational members negatively reacting towards those who take flexitime options, they have concerns about having difficulties in interacting with colleagues and having a feeling of disconnected from the workplace. This implies that in designing and modifying flexitime arrangements, organizations have to develop strategies to reduce such negative feelings as workplace flexibility strategies will continue to be popular in future.

Third, though flexitime arrangements in companies with smaller number of employees offered limited benefits, employees use the option. However, this implies that more positive attitudes associated with flexitime occur only when arrangements are employee driven. This situation raises questions about the role of HR managers in managing individuals' expectations and experiences in workplaces.

Forth, in competitive business sectors, organizations need to develop a diverse workforce into motivated and efficient employees. In this process, organizations must cope with employee attraction and retention issues. Findings of the study led to imply that flexitime could be used as a desirable feature to attract prospective employees and to boost the organization's reputation as an employer of choice. However, flexitime would not work as an effective strategy towards reducing labour turnover; hence it would not lead to save organization in recruitment and induction costs. However, organizations have to understand the needs of their targeted applicant pool and carefully consider recruitment implications of work arrangements when analysing costs associated with these policies. Further, in this connection, strategies with respect to people management should not be seen as strategies on their own, but must be considered as a part of the total approach of the company towards its people management.

Finally, the employers from the organizations without flexitime have to re-validate their perceptions towards flexitime. Thus, it is important to distinguish the psychological barriers from the operational constraints that impose limitations in the use of flexible arrangements. In this context, knowledge of employers regarding how flexibility can work and knowledge of employees of what it is possible for organizations to offer would appear as the key in distinguishing between actual and perceived incompatibility. Thus, it is not only that

employees experience the autonomy provided by flexitime, but also this autonomy has to be managed behaviourally. This implies that implementing flexitime in an organization could be considered as a change to structure and culture. The cultural change must be handled carefully and leadership for change is a necessary element. In this context, HR managers have a vital role to play in the process of making adjustments and adoptions to the new realities of workplace identifying them as opportunities

Limitations and future research

This study was confined to investigate organization led formal flexitime arrangements in software development companies based on the information collected utilizing self-report measures. As previously noted, very little work has been directed toward the identification of design factors for flexitime arrangements. The findings of the study do not close the door for further investigations. Future studies could be extended to investigate several other variables such as organizational culture in order to develop a better understanding of the optimum contexts for flexitime. Further, the study has not investigated flexitime effect on organizational performance, for example absenteeism, turnover or productivity that warrants further research, especially of longitudinal in nature. Furthermore, Kim and Campagna (1981) suggested that flexitime could have a positive influence on the reduction of commuting time and traffic congestion problems and parking problems. To study such effects at the country level from a people management practice might be valuable for countries that face with infrastructure difficulties. These all open the door for further investigations.

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Tables

Table I: Characteristics of the companies

Characteristic	Value label	Flexitime exists (n=15) F	Total sample (n=30)	
			F	%
Number of years in operation	Less than 4 years	2	9	30
	4 to 8 years	3	11	37
	More than 8 years	10	10	33
Number of employees	Less than 30	3	13	44
	30 to 60	3	5	16
	More than 60	9	12	40
Ownership	Local	4	13	43
	Joint venture	7	12	40
	Foreign	4	5	17

Table II: Characteristics of the employees

Characteristic	Value label	Flexitime exists (n=55)		Total sample (n=108)	
		F	%	F	%
Gender	Male	36	65	70	65
	Female	19	35	38	35
Highest level of education	Postgraduate Degree	6	26	7	6
	Bachelors Degree	35	63	67	62
	Diploma	14	11	34	32
Marital status	Married	21	38	42	39
	Unmarried	34	62	66	61
Number of employees in the current workplace	Less than 30	10	18	34	32
	30 to 60	18	33	25	23
	More than 60	27	49	49	45
Experience in the current workplace	Less than 4 years	36	65	66	61
	4 to 8 years	16	29	37	34
	More than 8 years	3	6	5	5

Table III: Correlations among study variables

Variable	1	2	3	4	5
1. Level of satisfaction with flexitime	--				
2. Gender	.217	--			
3. Marital status	.140	.081	--		
4. Highest level of education	.026	.030	.039	--	
5. Years of experience in current workplace	.000	.250*	.161	.030	--
6. Number of employees in the current workplace	.272*	.000	.190	.085	.079

Notes:

* $p < 0.05$, $n = 55$

Table IV: Attitudes towards flexitime

	Mean (n=55)	SD
Reduces stress	4.16	.56
Feels less restriction at work	3.62	.89
Helps to balance work and family life	4.40	.70
Helps to balance work and social life	4.24	.79
Enables to focus on job when at workplace	3.63	.91
Provides time for higher studies	3.28	.94
Motivates towards work	3.79	.68
Makes committed to work	3.44	.93
Reduces team spirit (N)	2.20	.73
Reduces workplace learning opportunities (N)	2.09	.74
Negatively impacts on career progress (N)	2.01	.53
Feels disconnected from workplace (N)	1.98	.73
Leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues (N)	2.12	.89
Workplace reacts negatively towards those who use flexitime (N)	1.71	.78
Leads to miss important workplace events (N)	1.83	.88

Table V: Attitudes towards flexitime by gender and marital status

	Gender (n=55)				Marital status (n=55)			
	Male Mean (SD)	Female Mean (SD)	t-test		Married Mean (SD)	Unmarried Mean (SD)	t-test	
			t	Sig.(2-tailed)			t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Reduces stress	4.08 (.60)	4.31 (.47)	1.45	.152	4.19 (.60)	4.14 (.55)	-.272	.787
Feels less restriction at work	3.54 (.85)	3.78 (.97)	.965	.339	3.52 (.98)	3.69 (.84)	.689	.494
Helps to balance work and family life	4.30 (.74)	4.57 (.60)	1.369	.117	4.28 (.71)	4.47 (.70)	.937	.353
Helps to balance work and social life	4.11 (.86)	4.47 (.61)	1.601	.115	4.20 (.83)	4.26 (.79)	.285	.777
Enables to focus on job when at workplace	3.71 (.85)	3.47 (1.02)	-.919	.362	3.76 (.94)	3.54 (.90)	-.843	.403
Provides time for higher studies	3.08 (.95)	3.63 (.83)	2.103	.040*	2.90 (.91)	3.50 (.89)	2.361	.022**
Motivates towards work	3.80 (.71)	3.77 (.64)	-.110	.913	3.90 (.78)	3.72 (.62)	-.882	.382
Makes committed to work	3.33 (1.01)	3.63 (.76)	1.124	.266	3.33 (1.11)	3.50 (.82)	.594	.557
Reduces team spirit (N)	2.14 (.77)	2.31 (.67)	.821	.415	2.15 (.74)	2.23 (.74)	.408	.685
Reduces workplace learning opportunities (N)	2.00 (.68)	2.26 (.80)	1.266	.211	2.04 (.74)	2.12 (.73)	.356	.723
Negatively impacts on career progress (N)	2.05 (.59)	1.94 (.40)	-.721	.474	1.90 (.53)	2.09 (.52)	1.261	.213
Feels disconnected from workplace (N)	2.11 (.78)	1.73 (.56)	-1.841	.071*	1.95 (.66)	2.00 (.77)	.232	.817
Leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues (N)	2.30 (.98)	1.73 (.56)	-2.732	.009**	2.28 (.95)	2.00 (.85)	- 1.152	.254
Workplace reacts negatively to people using flexitime (N)	1.83 (.84)	1.47 (.61)	-1.639	.107	1.66 (.73)	1.73 (.82)	.312	.756
Leads to miss important workplace events (N)	1.88 (.93)	1.73 (.80)	-.587	.560	1.70 (.73)	1.91 (.96)	.847	.401

Notes:

* p<0.05; **p<0.01

Table VI: Attitudes towards flexitime by highest level of education and number of employees

	Highest level of education				Sig.	Number of employees in the current workplace				Sig.
	Mean (SD)					Mean (SD)				
	Total	Diploma	Degree	Postgraduate		Total	<30	30-60	>60	
Reduces stress	4.16 (.56)	4.14 (.36)	4.14 (.64)	4.33 (.51)	.749	4.16 (.56)	3.90 A (.73)	4.00 B (.48)	4.37 AB (.49)	.024*
Feels less restriction at work	3.62 (.89)	3.57 (.75)	3.55 (.95)	4.16 (.75)	.303	3.62 (.89)	3.90 (.73)	3.61 (1.03)	3.53 (.85)	.561
Helps to balance work and family life	4.40 (.70)	4.35 (.63)	4.42 (.73)	4.33 (.81)	.925	4.40 (.70)	3.70 AB (.82)	4.61 A (.60)	4.51 B (.57)	.001**
Helps to balance work and social life	4.24 (.79)	4.15 (.68)	4.28 (.85)	4.16 (.75)	.859	4.24 (.79)	3.70 A (.94)	4.52 A (.62)	4.25 (.76)	.030*
Enables to focus on job when at workplace	3.62 (.91)	3.28 (.91)	3.64 (.88)	4.33 (.81)	.061	3.62 (.91)	3.70 (.94)	3.33 (.90)	3.80 (.89)	.236
Provides time for higher studies	3.27 (.94)	3.21 (1.18)	3.29 (.83)	3.33 (1.03)	.955	3.27 (.94)	3.22 (1.20)	3.38 (.97)	3.22 (.84)	.833
Motivates towards work	3.79 (.68)	3.76 (.72)	3.71 (.67)	4.33 (.51)	.119	3.79 (.68)	3.80 (.63)	3.70 (.77)	3.84 (.67)	.814
Makes committed to work	3.43 (.93)	3.57 (1.01)	3.31 (.93)	3.83 (.75)	.383	3.43 (.93)	3.30 (.94)	3.44 (.98)	3.48 (.93)	.876
Reduces team spirit (N)	2.20 (.73)	2.37 (.63)	2.20 (.71)	2.00 (1.09)	.706	2.20 (.73)	2.60 (1.07)	2.17 (.63)	2.07 (.61)	.154
Reduces workplace learning opportunities (N)	2.09 (.73)	2.28 (.611)	2.00 (.60)	2.16 (1.47)	.464	2.09 (.73)	2.66 AB (1.22)	1.94 A (.53)	2.00 B (.55)	.032*
Negatively impacts on career progress (N)	2.01 (.53)	2.07 (.47)	2.05 (.54)	1.66 (.51)	.231	2.02 (.53)	2.40 A (.51)	2.05 (.41)	1.84 A (.54)	.016*
Feels disconnected from workplace (N)	1.98 (.73)	2.14 (.66)	2.00 (.76)	1.50 (.54)	.195	1.98 (.73)	2.40 (.84)	1.88 (.75)	1.88 (.64)	.136
Leads to difficulties in interacting with colleagues (N)	2.10 (.89)	2.28 (.99)	1.97 (.78)	2.50 (1.22)	.290	2.10 (.89)	2.70 A (.94)	2.11 (.90)	1.88 A (.80)	.047*
Workplace reacts negatively to people using flexitime (N)	1.71 (.78)	2.00 (.87)	1.65 (.72)	1.33 (.81)	.180	1.70 (.78)	2.20 (.91)	1.61 (.84)	1.59 (.63)	.090
Leads to miss important workplace events (N)	1.83 (.88)	2.00 (1.00)	1.80 (.86)	1.66 (.81)	.704	1.83 (.88)	2.70 AB (1.05)	1.82 A (.95)	1.51 B (.50)	.001**

Notes:

* p<0.05; **p<0.01, n=55

The means followed by the same letter are significantly different from each other.

Table VII: Flexitime as a strategy to attract and retain employees

	Mean	SD
Reluctance to change the current employer because of flexitime (n=55) ¹	2.96	.92
Consider flexitime as important in future workplaces (n=55) ¹	3.95	.98
Prefer to have flexitime in future workplaces (n=53) ²	4.66	.47
Consider flexitime as important/prefer to have flexitime in future workplaces (n=108) ³	4.30	.93

Notes

¹ respondents from workplaces where flexitime exists

² respondents from workplaces where flexitime do not exist

³ total respondents

Table VIII: Reasons that hinder the use of flexitime

	Mean (n=15)	SD
Resistance from employees	2.07	.45
Company policies do not allow to introduce	4.20	.41
Nature of business activities/client-customer interactions does not allow to introduce	3.60	.74
Feeling of employees might misuse the freedom	4.00	.53
Reduces team spirit	4.27	.45
Reduces mutual learning	4.40	.51
Might loose integrity	3.73	.96
Difficulties in coordinating interactions	5.00	.00